

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1875	Kunio Yanagita	1910		1930		Japanese scholar and considered the father of Japanese native folkloristics, or minzokugaku	1875-1962
1875	Patrice Coirault	1927	No	1934		French high-ranking civil servant in the Ministry of Public Works and ethnomusicologist	1875-1959
1875	Konrad Nielsen	1896	1896	1947		Norwegian philologist	1875-1953
1875	Ferdinand Sommer	1896	1896	1940		German classical and Indo-European philologist	1875-1962
1875	Eduard Castle	1897	1897	1949		Austrian-German Germanist and literary historian	1875-1959
1875	Joel Elias Spingarn	1898		1939		American educator, literary critic, and civil rights activist	1875-1939
1875	Enno Littmann	1898	1898	1949		German orientalist	1875-1958
1875	Paul E. Kahle	1898	1898	1945		German Orientalist and scholar	1875-1964
1875	Edmund Crosby Quiggin	1898	1898	1920		British linguist and scholar	1875-1920
1875	Louis Herbert Gray	1899	1900	1944		American Orientalist	1875-1955
1875	Hardin Craig	1899	1899	1967		American Renaissance scholar and professor of English	1875-1968
1875	Elsie Clews Parsons	1899	1899	1941	w	American anthropologist, sociologist, folklorist, and feminist	1875-1941
1875	Diedrich Hermann Westermann	1900	No	1950		German missionary, Africanist, and linguist	1875-1956
1875	Roland Burrage Dixon	1900	1900	1934		American anthropologist	1875-1934
1875	Edgar Howard Sturtevant	1901	1901	1943		American linguist	1875-1952
1875	Rudolf Tombo Jr.	1901	1901	1914		German-American philologist who was associate professor of Germanic languages	1875-1914
1875	Joseph Vendryes	1902		1944		French Celtic linguist	1875-1960
1875	Natalie Curtis	1902	No	1920	w	American ethnomusicologist	1875-1921
1875	Georg Graf	1903	1903	1930		German Orientalist	1875-1955
1875	Hans Peder Steensby	1905	1905	1920		Danish ethnographer, geographer and professor	1875-1920
1875	Mario Roques	1906		1961		French scholar, professor of history of medieval literature and renowned Romance philologist	1875-1961
1875	Traian Bratu	1907	1907	1940		Romanian scholar of German language and literature	1875-1940
1875	Alexander William Mair	1908		1928		British Scottish scholar	1875-1928
1875	Joseph Castagné	1909		1935		French-Russian-French ethnographer and expert on Central Asia	1875-1958

1876 Shinmura Izuru	1910	1919	1961	Japanese linguist and essayist	1876-1967
1876 Paul Rivet	1912		1950	French ethnologist; he founded the Musée de l'Homme in 1937	1876-1958
1876 Matteo Marangoni	1920		1951	Italian art historian, art critic and composer	1876-1958
1876 George Cathcart Woolley	1922	No	1932	British colonial administrator in North Borneo (now Sabah), ethnographer and an ardent collector	1876-1947
1876 Robert Gauthiot	1898	1913	1914	French Orientalist, linguist and explorer	1876-1916
1876 Reginald Campbell Thompson	1898		1941	British archaeologist, assyriologist, and cuneiformist	1876-1941
1876 Eugen Mittwoch	1899	1899	1938	German the founder of Modern Islamic Studies in Germany	1876-1942
1876 Carl Heinrich Becker	1899	1899	1930	German orientalist and politician in Prussia	1876-1933
1876 Aleksandar Belić	1900	1900	1960	Serbian linguist and academic, President of Academy of science	1876-1960
1876 Felix Jacoby	1900	1900	1948	German classicist and philologist	1876-1959
1876 A. L. Kroeber	1901	1901	1947	American cultural anthropologist	1876-1960
1876 Israel Friedlander	1901	1901	1920	Polish rabbi, educator, translator, and biblical scholar	1876-1920
1876 Chauncey Brewster Tinker	1902	1902	1945	British scholar and Sterling Professor	1876-1963
1876 Ernst Bickel	1902		1948	German classical philologist	1876-1961
1876 William Witherle Lawrence	1902		1936	American philologist who served as Professor of English	1876-1936
1876 John Strong Perry Tatlock	1903	1903	1946	American literary scholar and medievalist	1876-1948
1876 Tenney Frank	1903	1903	1939	American prominent ancient historian and classical scholar	1876-1939
1876 Alphonse Bayot	1904	1904	1937	Belgian Romanist	1876-1937
1876 Stephen Herbert Langdon	1905	1905	1937	American-British Assyriologist	1876-1937
1876 Maurice Pézard	1905	1905	1923	French archaeologist and assyriologist	1876-1923
1876 Ivane Javakhishvili	1905		1940	Georgian historian and a linguist whose voluminous works heavily influenced the modern scholarship of the history and culture of Georgia	1876-1940
1876 Mary Inda Hussey	1906	1906	1941 w	American Assyriologist and professor	1876-1952
1877 Vladimir Minorsky	1911	No	1944	Russian Orientalist (Persian and Kurdish history, geography, literature, and culture)	1877-1966
1877 Ernest Tonnelat	1912	1912	1945	French Germanist and historian of literature	1877-1948

1877 Georges Contenau	1914	1923	1957	French archeologist, orientalist and religious historian who was an expert in the field of culture and religion of the civilizations of the Near and Middle East	1877-1964
1877 Ushinosuke Mori	1915	No	1926	Japanese anthropologist and folklorist	1877-1926
1877 Abraham Yahuda	1895		1942	Palestinian Jew polymath, teacher, writer, researcher, linguist, and collector of rare documents	1877-1951
1877 Ivy Kellerman Reed	1898	1902	1947 w	American author in the international language Esperanto	1877-1968
1877 Karl Jaberg	1900	1900	1948	Swiss linguist and dialectologist	1877-1958
1877 Alexander von Staël-Holstein	1900	1900	1937	Estonian German-baltic aristocrat, Russian and Estonian orientalist, sinologist, sanskritologist, specializing in Buddhist texts	1877-1937
1877 Zoltán Gombocz	1900	1900	1935	Hungarian scholar specializing in Finno-Ugric languages, but also in Turkic languages	1877-1935
1877 Arthur W. Ryder	1901	1901	1938	American professor of Sanskrit	1877-1938
1877 Fritz Graebner	1901	1901	1934	German geographer and ethnologist best known for his development of the theory of Kulturkreis, or culture circle	1877-1934
1877 Alfred Tozzer	1902	1904	1948	American anthropologist, archaeologist, linguist, and educator	1877-1954
1877 Walter Bauer	1902	1902	1946	German theologian, lexicographer of New Testament Greek, and scholar of the development of Early Christianity	1877-1960
1877 Hugo Gressmann	1902	1902	1927	German prominent Old Testament scholar in Protestant Germany	1877-1927
1877 Erland Nordenskiöld	1902		1932	Swedish archeologist and anthropologist	1877-1932
1877 Roland Grubb Kent	1903	1903	1947	American educator and a founder of the Linguistic Society of America (LSA)	1877-1952
1877 Hugo Obermaier	1904	1904	1939	German distinguished prehistorian and anthropologist who taught at various European centres of learning	1877-1946
1877 Bertha Phillpotts	1905	No	1932 w	British English scholar in Scandinavian languages, literature, history, archaeology and anthropology	1877-1932
1877 Maurice Garland Fulton	1906		1955	American historian and English professor	1877-1955

1877	Sextil Pușcariu	1906	1943	Romanian (Austro-Hungarian) linguist and philologist, also known for his involvement in administrative and party politics	1877-1948	
1877	Henri Breuil	1906	No	1947	French Catholic priest and member of the Society of Jesus, archaeologist, anthropologist, ethnologist and geologist	1877-1961
1877	J. O. Kinnaman	1907	1907	1961	American biblical scholar and biblical archaeologist	1877-1961
1877	Albert Dauzat	1909	1906	1955	French linguist specializing in toponymy and onomastics	1877-1955
1877	Jacques Bacot	1909		1954	French explorer and pioneering French Tibetologist	1877-1965
1878	Paul Hazard	1910	1910	1941	French professor and historian of ideas	1878-1944
1878	Thomas Athol Joyce	1910		1938	British anthropologist, expert on American and African Anthropology at the British Museum	1878-1942
1878	Hans Bauer	1910	1910	1937	German semitist	1878-1937
1878	Walter Evans-Wentz	1911	1911	1942	American anthropologist and writer who was a pioneer in the study of Tibetan Buddhism, and in transmission of Tibetan Buddhism to the Western world	1878-1965
1878	Edmond Vermeil	1912	1912	1958	French academic and specialist in the German culture	1878-1964
1878	Jules Marouzeau	1922		1964	French philologist	1878-1964
1878	Félix Faustino Outes	1899	1899	1938	Argentinean anthropologist, archeologist and linguist	1879-1939
1878	Gustav Neckel	1900	1900	1940	German scholar of medieval German studies and Old Norse	1878-1940
1878	Michail Arnaudov	1904	1904	1944	Bulgarian folklorist, literary historian, ethnographer	1878-1978
1878	Enrico Insabato	1904		1948	Italian orientalist and scholar of Islam, history of research on Ibadism	1878-1963
1878	Chariton Charitonidis	1904	1909	1940	Greek classical philologist, professor	1878-1954
1878	Oiva Tuulio	1907	1907	1941	Finnish linguist specializing in the Romance languages	1878-1941
1878	Austin Morris Harmon	1908	1908	1945	American classical scholar, mostly notable for his bilingual editions of Lucian's works in the Loeb Classical Library	1878-1950
1878	Aleksei Ivanovich Ivanov	1909	1913	1937	Russian Sinologist and Tangutologist	1878-1937
1879	Payson J. Treat	1910	1910	1945	American Japanologist	1879-1972
1879	Jean Deny	1911		1949	French grammarian, specialist of oriental languages	1879-1963
1879	Dumitru Caracostea	1913	1913	1948	Romanian folklorist, literary historian and critic	1879-1964
1879	Ali Akbar Dehkhodā	1916		1956	Iranian linguist	1879-1956

1879	Viljo Tarkiainen	1917	1917	1951	Finnish Finnish literary critic, critic and professor at the University of Helsinki	1879-1951
1879	Alfred Korzybski	1920	1943	1950	Polish-American independent scholar (developer a field called general semantics)	1879-1950
1879	Bedřich Hrozný	1900	No	1952	Czech orientalist and linguist	1879-1952
1879	Kazimieras Būga	1900		1924	Lithuanian linguist and philologist	1879-1924
1879	Alessandro Della Seta	1901	1901	1939	Italian Italian archaeologist specializing in Etruscology and Classical Archeology	1879-1944
1879	Ettore Bignone	1901	1901	1953	Italian classical philologist (with a focus on Greek studies) and historian of philosophy	1879-1953
1879	Truman Michelson	1903	1904	1938	American linguist and anthropologist	1879-1938
1879	John Erskine	1903	1903	1937	American educator and author, pianist and composer	1879-1951
1879	Max Ebert	1903		1929	German prehistorian known for his studies associated with the Baltic states and South Russia	1879-1929
1879	Wilhelm Kosch	1903	1903	1950	Austrian historian of literature and theatre and lexicographer	1879-1960
1879	Edward Robertson	1904	1962	1945	British Scottish academic, Professor of Semitic Studies	1879-1964
1879	Alan Gardiner	1904		1948	British English Egyptologist, linguist, philologist, and independent scholar	1879-1963
1879	Rafael Karsten	1905	1905	1946	Finnish social anthropologist and philosopher of religion, known especially for his work among the indigenous people of Southern America	1879-1956
1879	Charles Drouhet	1906	1909	1940	Romanian literary historian	1879-1940
1879	David Brainard Spooner	1906	1906	1925	American archaeologist and linguist	1879-1925
1879	Idris Bell	1906		1944	British museum curator, a British papyrologist (specialising in Roman Egypt) and a scholar of Welsh literature	1879-1967
1879	Alexander Freiman	1906	1906	1956	Polish-Russian researcher of the Iranian languages	1879-1968
1879	Karl Young	1907	1907	1943	American professor of English, medievalist, and theatre historian	1879-1943
1879	Margarete Bieber	1907	1907	1948 w	German-American art historian, classical archaeologist and professor	1879-1978
1879	Samuel Barrett	1908	1908	1939	American anthropologist and linguist (Native American peoples)	1879-1965

1879 Elias Avery Lowe	1908	1908	1953	Russian-American palaeographer	1879-1969
1879 Barbara Freire-Marreco	1908 No		1959 w	British English anthropologist and folklorist.	1879-1967
1879 Knud Rasmussen	1908 No		1933	Greenlandic–Danish polar explorer and anthropologist, the "father of Eskimology"	1879-1933
1879 Alfred Ernout	1908	1908	1946	French philologist, specialized in the Latin language	1879-1973
1879 Agathe Lasch	1909	1909	1934 w	German philologist, first female professor of German studies in Germany	1879-1942